

USE OF ART THERAPY TO ELIMINATE AGGRESSION

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ABSTRACT

This article provides sufficient information on how to eliminate aggression using art therapy. Art therapy provides an opportunity to express creative abilities along with healing through art.

Art therapy helps to discover the world, learn the properties of objects and substances, and develop fine motor skills. According to the theory of K. Rudestam, the tasks of art therapy are as follows: Allocating a socially acceptable place for aggression and other negative emotions; facilitating the process of treatment (psychotherapy) as an auxiliary method; obtaining material for psychodiagnostics, working with suppressed thoughts and feelings; contact with the client; development of self-control; focus on feelings; develop creativity and increase self-esteem.

The reasons for aggression may be different, but regardless of them, the main problem in this case is that the child does not know how to deal with his emotions. By attacking someone, he gets some kind of freedom, relief. Here it is important to teach him not to harm others, to transfer anger and frustration to alien things. Such actions also lead to emotional release. However, it is better to teach your child to find a way out of his feelings in visual arts and turn to art therapy.

Art therapy in working with aggressive children follows:

- provide the young patient with a list of acceptable ways to express strong emotions. In practice, the art therapist tells and shows the child how he can express his feelings, apart from destructive behavior;
- help to understand feelings of anger and eliminate aggression;
- verbal communication with feelings of anger. Instead of harming the child, the therapist teaches him to express his thoughts to those who have caused strong anger;
- discuss the problem with your child.

An individual approach is very important in this matter. All children are different, with different learning methods, and therefore art therapy can never be simple "take paper, pencil and draw". Some children are excited to start drawing, while others resist. The reasons for

this may be internal uncertainty, the complexity of the subject given for the drawing, and a number of other factors. It is especially important to choose the subjects of the use of visual arts. While some children are more comfortable creating things with a narrow theme set by an art therapist, others can only fully engage in the process when given the freedom to choose. For example, free drawing. It is also necessary to take into account the personal fears and phobias of the small patient: if the child is afraid of cars, the topic of "drawing the road" is unacceptable for him. The main task of an art therapist during individual sessions is to establish communication and trusting relationships. Even if the child categorically refuses to draw or sculpt something, an experienced specialist will still try to find other ways to express the patient's feelings. For example, he can take over the main work and burn and draw something together with the child. It is important that the child helps in this process, so that he fully participates in the art therapy process.

Group training is a more complex process, because the child is already learning to behave like other children in the group. In this case, it is important that the art therapist selects children according to their interests, abilities and ability to concentrate. It is necessary to develop a high tolerance for others, which is achieved due to the common interests and enthusiasm of young patients. Art therapy almost always begins with individual sessions, and only then group therapy is gradually introduced. Individual assignments are given to each member of the group, but at the same time, they should not contradict the general topics. If the child behaves aggressively for any reason, it is necessary to work with him, to give the child the opportunity to express his feelings in a way that does not use violence against other people. If, after explanations and punishments, during the conflict, the child simply touches the other, but does not hit, that is good, but it is not enough.

In conclusion, the main difference between art therapy and other psychotherapeutic practices is the use of non-verbal communication as the main mechanism of communicating information to people. Its basis consists of practical exercises that help a person find answers to any questions, overcome fear, soften and release aggression.

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